

Experimental

A standard solution of molybdenum(VI) was prepared by dissolving ammonium molybdate, A.R. in glass distilled water. The amount of molybdenum in this solution was determined using 8-hydroxyquinoline².

A systronic pH meter, type 322 was used for pH measurements. The precipitated complex was collected on Whatman filter paper (No. 42, 11 cm) and ignited in silica crucible.

The reagent, N-hydroxy-N-*p*-chlorophenyl-N'-(2,3-dimethyl)phenyl-*p*-toluamidine hydrochloride, was prepared by the condensation of N-(2,3-dimethyl)phenyl-*p*-toluimidoyl chloride with equimolar N-*p*-chlorophenyl hydroxylamine in ether medium. A 3% (w/v) alcoholic solution of the reagent was used for precipitation purposes. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Recommended procedure: An aliquot of the test solution, containing 4-40 mg of the metal is diluted to 200 ml in a 400 ml beaker. The pH of the solution is adjusted between 4.5-6.5 using acetic acid and dilute ammonia. The solution is warmed to 60-70° and 3% alcoholic solution of the reagent (20 ml per 30 mg molybdenum) is added slowly with constant stirring. The instantaneously precipitated orange-yellow complex is digested on water bath for 15-20 min with occasional stirring and then filtered through a Whatman filter paper. The complex is washed several times with warm water and dried at 105° for 20-25 min. It is then transferred along with the filter paper to a silica crucible and carefully ignited at 500-550° till MoO₃ acquires a bright appearance with no trace of black particles. The amount of the metal is calculated from the weight of MoO₃, using the conversion factor of 0.66654.

Optimum experimental conditions: The precipitation of molybdenum complex commences at pH 0.8 and is quantitative in the pH range 3.0-7.0. However, the most suitable pH range for the determination of molybdenum is 4.5-6.5, in which a granular and easily filtrable precipitate is obtained.

At least 2.0-2.5 times the theoretical quantity of the reagent is necessary for complete precipitation. An excess of reagent (0.7 g) in a final volume of 200 ml have no interfering effect on the determination. In practice, for each mg of molybdenum, 20 mg of the reagent was employed.

Properties and composition of the complex: The dioxomolybdenum complex was orange-yellow in colour and soluble in common organic solvents such as alcohol, acetone, chloroform, benzene, carbon tetrachloride. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were estimated by combustion method. (Found: Mo, 11.12; C, 61.69; H, 4.65; N, 6.47. Calcd. for MoO₂(C₂₂H₂₀N₂OCl)₂; Mo, 11.21; C, 61.75; H, 4.67; N, 6.55%). The 1:2 stoichiometry is confirmed by conductometric and pH metric studies. The formula of the complex may therefore be represented as MoO₂(C₂₂H₂₀N₂OCl)₂.

Infrared spectra: The displacement of C=N (1610 cm⁻¹) and N-O (930 cm⁻¹) stretching frequencies to 1575 and 960 cm⁻¹, respectively along with the disappearance of the =N⁺-H frequency (2550 cm⁻¹) of the free ligand in the complex suggest the formation of M-O bond, deprotonation of the azomethine nitrogen atom (C-N⁺-H) and metal coordination through it by forming C=N. M type of bond. The presence of MoO₂ group has been confirmed from the ir spectrum of the complex. A strong band at 920 cm⁻¹ is truly indicative of a O=Mo=O species, as oxo-metal cation such as Mo=O, involving a single oxygen metal multiple covalent bond absorbs at considerably higher region around 970-980 cm⁻¹. Similar assignments of dioxomolybdenum group has been made to the presence of a strong band around 910-920 cm⁻¹ in the molybdenum complexes of several other ligands such as oxine, N-benzoylphenyl hydroxylamine and Schiff bases.

Effect of diverse ions: The effect of diverse ions on the gravimetric determination of molybdenum(VI) with the reagent has been studied. Chloride, bromide, nitrate, sulphate, oxalate, citrate, borate, phosphate and alkali metals do not interfere upto 500 mg. The tolerance limits of other ions causing an error less than 2% are given in parenthesis (in mg) Co²⁺(90); Mn²⁺(100); Zn²⁺(120); Al³⁺(95); Hg²⁺(70); Bi³⁺(100); Th⁴⁺(160); Zr⁴⁺(80); Ti³⁺(160); La³⁺(160). The interference due to Cu²⁺(100); Ni²⁺(90); Cr³⁺(110); Fe³⁺(90) and V⁵⁺(25) could be avoided in presence of 2 g EDTA. Ti⁴⁺(30) could be masked with 5 ml H₂O₂ (20 vol) and 20 ml 10% EDTA. In presence of UO₂²⁺(130) the determination should be carried out at pH 3.2. The interference due to Nb⁵⁺ and Ta⁵⁺(50) could be eliminated by using tartaric acid (1 g) and NH₄-HF₂(500 mg). However, the interference due to W⁶⁺ could not be overcome.

References

1. I. M. KOLTHOFF and E. B. SANDELL, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", MacMillan Co., New York, 1964, p. 694.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green and Co. Ltd., London, 1964, p. 508.
3. S. K. SINHA and S. C. SHOMK, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1961, 24, 83.

A New Method for Extractive Photometric Determination of Copper and Iron in Alloy Steel

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QUINOLINE-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (QAT) has been used in this laboratory for extractive spectrophotometric determination of nickel and palladium¹. Extension of these studies revealed

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF FOREIGN IONS ON THE EXTRACTION OF COPPER (10 µg) AND IRON (25 µg)

Ions added	Tolerance limit, mg		Ions added	Tolerance limit, mg	
	Copper	Iron		Copper	Iron
Cobalt(II)	0.15	0.1	Lanthanum(III)	0.25	0.1
Zinc(II)	None	0.15	Platinum(IV)	—	0.1
Manganese(II)	0.05	0.15	Thorium(IV)	0.1	0.1
Tin(II)	2	None	Vanadium(V)	1.5	2.5
Lead(II)	0.05	0.8	Uranium(VI)	0.3	0.5
Palladium(II)	None	0.15	Molybdenum(VI)	1.5	0.1
Copper(II)	—	0.05*	Tungsten(VI)	5	0.25
Nickel(II)	0.05	0.05	Osmium(VIII)	0.1	0.1
Iron(III)	0.02	—	Tartrate	None	1.5
Aluminium(III)	0.01	0.15	Fluoride	None	0.5
Bismuth(III)	0.15	2.5	Chloride	1	5
Chromium(III)	0.15	0.10	EDTA	None	0.5
Gold(III)	0.25	0.15	Nitrate	None	1
Ruthenium(III)	0.5	0.1	Citrate	0.1	0.25
			Ascorbate	None	0.5

* masked with EDTA

that QAT also reacts selectively with divalent iron and copper at pH 7.5 and the extracted green and lemon yellow complexes are well suited for spectrophotometric determination of iron and copper at 600 and 430 nm, respectively.

Experimental

Absorption measurements were taken on a Zeiss spectrophotometer using 1 cm quartz cells. pH was measured on a Philips pH meter.

A 0.05% (w/v) solution of QAT in 1 : 1 DMF – H₂O was used for copper and iron determination. Stock solutions of copper (2.0×10^{-4} M) and iron (2.2×10^{-4} M) were prepared by dissolving analytical grade cupric sulphate and Mohr's salt and standardized by known methods. The solutions of lower concentration were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solutions.

A 3% aqueous hydroxylamine hydrochloride solution was used for the reduction of iron(III).

All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Recommended extraction procedure for copper and iron :

An aliquot of the sample solution (20 ml) containing either 5.25 µg copper or 5.60 µg iron (1 ml of 3% aqueous hydroxylamine hydrochloride is added to prevent atmospheric oxidation of iron) is taken and 4 ml of 0.05% QAT solution is added. The pH of the solution is adjusted to 7.5 (with NaOH/H₂SO₄) in a total volume of 25 ml. The solution is transferred to a separating funnel and extracted twice, for 20 sec each time, with two 5 ml portions of chloroform. The organic phase is collected, dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance of the lemon yellow complex (Cu – QAT) or the green complex (Fe – QAT) is measured at 430 and 600 nm, respectively against a reagent blank prepared in the same manner. Copper or iron contents are computed from calibration graph.

Results and Discussion

Spectral characteristics and extraction conditions for copper and iron :

The absorption spectrum of Cu – QAT and Fe – QAT complexes extracted into chloroform at pH 7.5 show maximum absorbance at 430 and 600 nm, respectively. The optimum pH range for extraction of both iron and copper is 7.2-8.0. Beer's law holds good over the concentration range of 5-25 µg copper and 5-60 µg iron per 10 ml of the organic phase. Various solvents were tried to extract the copper and iron complexes. Chloroform was found to be the only effective solvent for quantitative extraction of copper-QAT whereas both chloroform and isoamyl alcohol provided quantitative extraction for Fe(QAT). Extraction was incomplete in all other solvents. 4 ml of 0.05% QAT solution and 20 sec extraction time are adequate for complete colour development of copper or iron complexes. Both the complexes are stable for 30 min. The molar absorptivities (and dissociation constants) of copper and iron complexes are found to be 1.33×10^4 l mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (3.89×10^{-10}) and 3.91×10^3 l mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (5.32×10^{-7}), respectively.

The precision of the method is fairly good. The standard deviation of the mean absorbance was found to be 0.009 and 0.003 for Cu (10 µg) and Fe (25 µg), respectively. The coefficient of variation was 4.5 and 2.0%, respectively.

Effect of foreign ions :

A number of representative ions were examined for their interference in the determination of copper and iron by the recommended procedure. The tolerance limit (Table 1) was set at the amount required to cause less than 1% error in the recovery of copper and iron. In the copper estimation, ions such as zinc, palladium, iron and complexing anions interfere. The interference due to iron (milligram amount) and zinc is eliminated by their prior extraction with TOA². Lead, nickel, iron and manganese are tolerated at trace concentrations (50 µg). Iron

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estimation by the proposed method is interfered severely by tin(II) whereas copper, nickel and rhodium(III) are tolerated at trace concentrations.

Applications to analysis of steel, brass and nickel-silver :

Copper and iron are found in association with metal ions such as Mn, Cr, Ni, Mo, Pb, Zn and Bi in steel, brass and nickel-silver alloy. Some of these cations specially zinc and iron interfere in the determination of iron and copper by the proposed method. However, their interference could be removed by prior extraction with TOA^a. This increases the specificity of the proposed method. The method is applied to the analysis of steel, brass and nickel-silver. The procedure for preparation of the

sample is described elsewhere^a. The relative error in the recovery of iron from steel is between 0.33 to 0.77% whereas the same for copper recovery from steel, brass and nickel-silver is between 0.73 to 1.4%.

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References

1. D. V. KHASNIS and V. M. SHINDE, *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 593.
2. P. S. PATIL, and V. M. SHINDE, *Microchim. Acta (Wien)*, 1977, **2**, 207.